

Generalized Fused Lasso for Treatment Pooling in Network Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

This work develops a generalized fused lasso (GFL) approach to fitting contrast-based network meta-analysis (NMA) models. The GFL method penalizes all pairwise differences between treatments, resulting in pooling of some treatments that are not sufficiently different. This approach offers an intriguing avenue for potentially mitigating biases in treatment rankings and multiple comparison issues.

To fit contrast-based NMA models within the GFL framework, we formulate the models as generalized least squares problems, where the precision matrix depends on the standard error in the data, the estimated between-study heterogeneity and the correlation between contrasts in multi-arm studies. By utilizing a Cholesky decomposition of the precision matrix, we linearly transform the data vector and design matrix to frame NMA within the GFL framework. We demonstrate how to construct the GFL penalty such that every pairwise difference is penalized similarly. The method is straightforward to implement in R via the “genlasso” package, and runs instantaneously, contrary to other regularization approaches that are Bayesian.

A simulation study confirms the ability of the GFL approach to pool treatments that have the same (or similar) effects while also revealing when, and to what extent, incorrect pooling may occur. Finally, the novel GFL-NMA method is applied to real-world datasets on Parkinson’s and diabetes. In both cases, the full (standard) NMA model was not favored compared to the best fitting GFL-NMA model with AICc selection of the tuning parameter ($\Delta AICc > 9$).

Key Words: model selection, multiple comparisons, parsimony, regularization, sparsity, treatment ranking.

1 Introduction

Network meta-analysis (NMA) is an extension of traditional (pairwise) meta-analysis, designed to synthesize quantitative evidence from a systematic literature review of randomized clinical trials concerning more than two treatments (Lumley, 2002; Dias et al., 2018, 2011). This statistical technique allows for the estimation of pairwise differences in treatment effects and treatment rankings. By combining data from multiple trials, NMA can provide a more comprehensive and accurate assessment of treatment effectiveness, facilitating evidence-based decision-making in clinical practice.

Growing concerns have emerged in recent literature about the validity of NMA conclusions, especially with regards to multiple comparison issues (Efthimiou and White, 2020; Del Re et al., 2013) and the interpretation and statistical properties of ranking probabilities (Kibret et al., 2014; Trinquart et al., 2016; Daly et al., 2019; Chiochia et al., 2020). For example, Kibret et al. (2014) conducted a simulation study which revealed that treatment rankings are influenced by the number of trials and network structure. Treatments with fewer trials tend to receive positively biased rankings, while extensively studied treatments may have negatively biased rankings. Consequently, this can lead to inaccurate rankings, favouring less-researched and inferior treatments over well-established ones.

Moreover, Efthimiou and White (2020) provide a comprehensive review and analysis of the multiple comparisons problem in NMA. This issue is critical because it can cause seriously inflated false positive rates, especially when dealing with a large number of treatments. The prevalence of a large number of treatments within networks of evidence is expected to increase over time as more treatment options are developed and studied. For instance, in less than a decade, Cipriani et al. (2018) expanded upon the evidence base established in Cipriani et al. (2009), which initially covered 12 antidepressant treatments, and extended it to include 21 treatments along with a placebo group. To address the multiple comparison issue, Efthimiou and White (2020) propose Bayesian models that assume exchangeable treatment effects. While these models offer potential solutions, they require subjective prior knowledge about potential similarities among treatments within the network. In a similar vein, Barrientos et al. (2022) proposed a nonparametric Bayesian approach to allow ties between treatments by employing a Dirichlet Process Spike-Slab model. However, the complexity involved in implementing and interpreting this method may be discouraging to applied NMA modelers.

Our paper proposes an alternative frequentist regularization method to the existing Bayesian methods presented in the previous paragraph. Specifically, we introduce a Generalized Fused Lasso (GFL) approach for network meta-analysis. This method accomplishes two key objectives simultaneously: it applies equal penalties to all pairwise treatment differences and pools similar treatments together. This pooling reduces the number of parameters in the model. Compared to existing approaches, the novel approach has the advantage of being completely data-driven (i.e. it avoids the use of subjective prior knowledge about potential similarities among treatments, which risks being inaccurate) and also of being simple to implement with a fast run time. The fast run time is achieved even in large networks where the number of potential pooling variations can be very large (e.g. 15 treatments may be pooled in 1.3×10^9 different ways; 20 treatments may be pooled in 5.1×10^{13} different ways, see Table 7).

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the fundamental principles and key concepts of Generalized Fused Lasso (GFL) and Network Meta-Analysis (NMA) models, which form the basis for this work. Section 3 presents the technical details of implementing contrast-based NMA models within a GFL framework. In Section 4, a simulation study is conducted to assess the performance of the proposed method. Section 5 discusses the application of the GFL-based NMA method to two real-world datasets. Section 6 provides a discussion.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Generalized Fused Lasso

Lasso, short for "Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator", is a widely recognized technique that penalises the sum of the absolute values of coefficients (l_1 norm) in a least squares regression (Tibshirani, 1996). By employing this penalty, Lasso has the capability to perform variable selection and parameter estimation simultaneously, forcing some coefficients to become exactly zero. The formula for Lasso is given by:

$$\underset{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^p}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda \|\beta\|_1, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a response vector, $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$ is a matrix of predictors, $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the coefficient vector, and $\lambda \geq 0$ is a tuning parameter. $\|\cdot\|_2$ represents the l_2 norm while $\|\cdot\|_1$ represents the l_1 norm.

Lasso is in fact a special case of a larger class of problems, where any linear transformation of the coefficients may be penalized with an l_1 norm. These problems are called Generalized Lasso

(Tibshirani and Taylor, 2011) and can be mathematically expressed as:

$$\underset{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^p}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{D}\beta\|_1, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times p}$ is a specified penalty matrix with m rows, and the design matrix \mathbf{X} has full column rank. An efficient path algorithm, developed by Tibshirani and Taylor (2011) can be used to quickly obtain the solution to (2) as a function of λ , for any matrix \mathbf{D} . Similar to the Lasso, the solution for the Generalized Lasso is also a continuous piece-wise linear function of λ . An example of coordinate path can be seen in Figure 5.

The choice of matrix \mathbf{D} in the generalized lasso formulation allows for the construction of different types of problems such as the fused lasso, trend filtering, and wavelet smoothing. In fused lasso (Tibshirani and Taylor, 2011), the objective is to penalize the differences between adjacent parameters. \mathbf{D} is an $m \times p$ matrix, where each row contains a '1' and '-1' at appropriate positions. This penalty structure is often used to penalize the differences between adjacent parameters in a time series, known as 1D fused lasso (Tibshirani and Taylor, 2011). In this case, \mathbf{D} takes the form of the following $(p-1) \times p$ matrix:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & -1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

When additional penalties are imposed on the coefficients themselves, the class of problems is called sparse fused lasso (Tibshirani and Taylor, 2011) and an $p \times p$ identity matrix is appended to the rows of \mathbf{D} , as follows:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Alternatively, the sparse fused lasso optimization problem can be expressed as

$$\underset{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^p}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^p |\beta_i| + \lambda_2 \sum_{i=2}^p |\beta_i - \beta_{i-1}|, \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \geq 0$ are tuning parameters. The solution to this problem tends to be smooth and sparse since the l_1 norm penalty is applied on both single coefficients and consecutive pairs. This problem was previously introduced by Tibshirani et al. (2004).

As pointed out by Tibshirani and Taylor (2011), the idea of adjacency in the sparse fused lasso can be extended by defining adjacency according to an arbitrary graph structure. Define G as a graph with nodes V and edges E , where nodes on the graph correspond to specific β coefficients and edges indicate which coefficient differences to penalize. Then, problem (4) is called Generalized Fused Lasso (GFL) (see e.g. Xin et al. (2016)):

$$\underset{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^p}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^p |\beta_i| + \lambda_2 \sum_{(i,j) \in E} |\beta_i - \beta_j|. \quad (4)$$

The R package “genlasso” easily fits such models via the function *fusedlasso*.

2.2 Network Meta-Analysis Models

There are multiple types of network meta-analysis models available for analysing aggregate data from randomized trials. Most published network meta-analyses use contrast-based models which assume that relative treatment effects are exchangeable across studies, while absolute treatment effects are not. Arm-based models are a more recent development, however they may not respect randomization (Karahalios et al., 2022). Generally, contrast-based models are the gold standard as they are a natural extension of pairwise meta-analysis which respects randomization. We will focus on contrast-based models in this paper. Contrast-based models typically assume consistency, meaning that for any three treatments A, B and C in the network, the effect of treatment C relative to B, denoted as d_{BC} , can be obtained by subtracting the relative effect d_{AB} (the effect of treatment B relative to A) from the relative effect d_{AC} (the effect of treatment C relative to A). In other words, $d_{BC} = d_{AC} - d_{AB}$, on a relevant scale.

In some NMAs, study results may be available in each arm (requiring arm-based likelihoods) while in other NMAs, study results are available as contrasts between arms (requiring contrast-based likelihoods). Example of contrasts may be: mean differences (standardized or not), log odds ratios, log relative risks or log hazard ratios, available along with their sample variances. Models where the response variable is a contrast may either model all $\binom{T_i}{2}$ contrasts in any given study i of T_i treatments or an independent subset of $T_i - 1$ contrasts. Rucker and Schwarzer (2014) showed that the two approaches are equivalent. Models that incorporate between-study heterogeneity are commonly called random-effect models, while models that assume no such heterogeneity are called fixed-effect models. Both frequentist and Bayesian approaches to NMA have been developed and are commonly employed (Dias et al., 2018).

Study i	Treatments	Contrast j	Description	$y_{i,j}$	$v_{i,j}$
1	{Plac, Ropi}	1	Plac - Ropi	0.31	0.45
2	{Plac, Pram}	1	Plac - Pram	1.70	0.15
3	{Plac, Pram, Brom}	1	Plac - Brom	0.90	0.48
		2	Pram - Brom	-1.40	0.49
		3	Plac - Pram	2.30	0.52
4	{Ropi, Brom}	1	Ropi - Brom	0.35	0.20
5	{Ropi, Brom}	1	Ropi - Brom	-0.55	0.31
6	{Brom, Cabe}	1	Brom - Cabe	0.30	0.08
7	{Brom, Cabe}	1	Brom - Cabe	0.30	0.10

Table 1: An example of contrast-based network meta-analysis with $M = 7$ studies and $T = 5$ treatments: Plac, Pram, Brom, Ropi, and Cabe. Studies 1, 2 and 4-7 have two arms while study 3 has three arms. The third contrast in study 3 is redundant (not independent from contrasts 1 and 2), therefore y_{33} is not included in the response vector in our modeling. More information about this example will be given in Section 5.1.

While there are various model formulations available for network meta-analysis, this paper specifically utilizes frequentist contrast-based models that take contrast-level data as the response variable. These models are chosen because they will allow for regularization via the GFL method in section 3, as they can be formulated as weighted least squares or generalized least squares problems. It is important to note that hierarchical modeling - commonly used in Bayesian analysis - and generalized linear models - commonly used with arm-based likelihood - do not directly align with the GFL framework. Therefore, the choice of frequentist contrast-based models and their compatibility with the GFL approach are key considerations in this paper. In situations where the data obtained from the systematic literature review is initially at the arm-level, it can be transformed into contrast-level data to satisfy our modeling approach (Borenstein et al., 2009).

Consider a collection of studies $i = 1, \dots, M$ with T_i representing the number of treatments in study i , and $C_i = T_i - 1$ representing the number of independent contrasts from study i . Define $\mathbf{y}_i = (y_{i,1}, \dots, y_{i,C_i})'$ as the vector of observed independent contrasts for study i , where $y_{i,j}$ represents the average effect for the j th contrast in study i . Let T be the total number of treatments across studies, then only $T - 1$ underlying means are needed by the consistency of NMA (Lumley, 2002). Define $\mathbf{d} = (d_{1,2}, \dots, d_{1,T-1})'$, a vector of underlying means for a set of independent contrasts, where 1 represents a common reference treatment. Within study i , the contrast-level data may be modeled as (Salanti et al., 2007):

$$\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{d} + \mathbf{u}_i + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_i, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{X}_i is a $C_i \times (T-1)$ design matrix for study i with each row defining a contrast using a 1 and -1 to indicate the treatments being compared and zeros otherwise. In addition, $\mathbf{u}_i = (u_{i,1}, \dots, u_{i,C_i})'$ is a vector of random effects contributing heterogeneity between studies, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_i = (\epsilon_{i,1}, \dots, \epsilon_{i,C_i})'$ is the random error in \mathbf{y}_i with distributions:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_i &\sim MVN_{C_i}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i), \\ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_i &\sim MVN_{C_i}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{V}_i), \end{aligned}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_i$ and \mathbf{V}_i are the corresponding variance-covariance matrices for study i depending on the different number of treatments in the studies, assuming each contrast has same degree of heterogeneity. When i is a two-arm study, $\mathbf{V}_i = v_i$ and $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_i = \tau^2$, where v_i represents the observed sample variance for y_i (extracted from the systematic literature review and reflecting the variation between individuals within study i) and τ^2 is a parameter representing the between-study heterogeneity. When i is a multi-arm study, $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_i$ and \mathbf{V}_i are $C_i \times C_i$ variance-covariance matrices with forms:

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \tau^2 & 0.5\tau^2 & \dots & 0.5\tau^2 \\ 0.5\tau^2 & \tau^2 & \dots & 0.5\tau^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0.5\tau^2 & 0.5\tau^2 & \dots & \tau^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \begin{pmatrix} v_{i,1} & v_{i,1,2} & \dots & v_{i,1,T_i-1} \\ v_{i,1,2} & v_{i,2} & \dots & v_{i,2,T_i-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ v_{i,1,T_i-1} & v_{i,2,T_i-1} & \dots & v_{i,T_i-1} \end{pmatrix},$$

where covariance terms of $0.5\tau^2$ for any pair of contrasts in study i assume that each contrast has the same degree of heterogeneity (Salanti et al., 2007). In addition, $v_{i,j}$ is the observed sample variance of $y_{i,j}$ and $v_{i,j,k}$ are observed sample covariances (extracted from the systematic literature review).

Aggregating all the studies in a single model with $\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{y}_1 \dots \mathbf{y}_M)'$, $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{X}_1 \dots \mathbf{X}_M)'$, $\mathbf{u} = (\mathbf{u}_1 \dots \mathbf{u}_M)'$, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = (\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_1 \dots \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_M)'$, gives the form:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{d} + \mathbf{u} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad (6)$$

with the random components in the model, \mathbf{u} and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &\sim MVN_{\sum_i (T_i - 1)}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \quad \boldsymbol{\Omega} = \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\Omega}_i) \\ \boldsymbol{\epsilon} &\sim MVN_{\sum_i (T_i - 1)}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{V}), \quad \mathbf{V} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{V}_i). \end{aligned}$$

Consider Table 1 as an example, which includes 6 two-arm studies (Study 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7) and a multi-arm study (Study 3). The network plot for this data is given in Figure 3a. The random effects

NMA model is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_{1,1} \\ y_{2,1} \\ y_{3,1} \\ y_{3,2} \\ y_{4,1} \\ y_{5,1} \\ y_{6,1} \\ y_{7,1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} d_{Plac,Brom} \\ d_{Plac,Cabe} \\ d_{Plac,Pram} \\ d_{Plac,Ropi} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} u_{1,1} \\ u_{2,1} \\ u_{3,1} \\ u_{3,2} \\ u_{4,1} \\ u_{5,1} \\ u_{6,1} \\ u_{7,1} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{1,1} \\ \epsilon_{2,1} \\ \epsilon_{3,1} \\ \epsilon_{3,2} \\ \epsilon_{4,1} \\ \epsilon_{5,1} \\ \epsilon_{6,1} \\ \epsilon_{7,1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

with variance-covariance matrices

$$\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} \tau^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \tau^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau^2 & 0.5\tau^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.5\tau^2 & \tau^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} v_{1,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & v_{2,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & v_{3,1} & v_{3,1,2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & v_{3,1,2} & v_{3,2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & v_{4,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & v_{5,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & v_{6,1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & v_{7,1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

While $v_{3,1,2}$ is not given directly in Table 1, it can be computed from the dependent case of the Variance Sum Law: $v_{3,3} = v_{3,1} + v_{3,2} - 2v_{3,1,2}$ implies $v_{3,1,2} = 0.225$ (Dias et al., 2018). Note that this covariance term is also equal to the observed variance in the Brom arm of study 3, since Brom is common to contrasts 1 and 2. An alternative to calculating this value may be to extract this arm-level variance from the systematic literature review.

Note finally that τ is unknown, and therefore fitting model (6) in a frequentist framework requires τ be replaced by an estimate $\hat{\tau}$. This estimate may be obtained via restricted maximum likelihood (Dias et al., 2011) or the generalized DerSimonian-Laird estimator (Böhning et al., 2002). Alternatively, setting $\tau = 0$ imposes the assumption of no between-study heterogeneity also called fixed-effect models, as opposed to models with $\tau > 0$ which are called random-effects models.

3 Methods

In this section, we present a GFL framework specifically designed for pooling similar treatments in a network meta-analysis. We term this approach GFL-NMA. Applying GFL to NMA is not straightforward due to the heteroscedastic variance in NMA models, which is different from the assumption of a homoscedastic variance with form $\sigma^2 I$ required by GFL, where σ^2 is a constant. To address this issue, we modify the presentation of the NMA model described in equation (6) from Section 2.2. By aggregating the random effect and residual error into a single error term, $\epsilon^* = \mathbf{u} + \epsilon$, we can express the NMA model more concisely as a linear regression model:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{d} + \epsilon^* \quad (8)$$

with $\epsilon^* \sim MVN(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma)$ and $\Sigma \equiv \Omega + \mathbf{V} = \text{diag}(\Omega_i + \mathbf{V}_i)$ by the property of multivariate normal distribution. For two-arm studies, we have $\Omega_i + \mathbf{V}_i = \tau^2 + v_i$, a scalar, which implies that Σ is a diagonal matrix. However, for multi-arm studies, we have a block-diagonal matrix:

$$\Omega_i + \mathbf{V}_i = \begin{pmatrix} \tau^2 + v_{i,1} & 0.5\tau^2 + v_{i,1,2} & \cdots & 0.5\tau^2 + v_{i,1,T_i-1} \\ 0.5\tau^2 + v_{i,1,2} & \tau^2 + v_{i,2} & \cdots & 0.5\tau^2 + v_{i,2,T_i-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0.5\tau^2 + v_{i,1,T_i-1} & 0.5\tau^2 + v_{i,2,T_i-1} & \cdots & \tau^2 + v_{i,T_i-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then, for instance, the matrix Σ for the example given in Table 1 is

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \tau^2 + v_{1,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \tau^2 + v_{2,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau^2 + v_{3,1} & 0.5\tau^2 + v_{3,1,2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.5\tau^2 + v_{3,1,2} & \tau^2 + v_{3,2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 + v_{4,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 + v_{5,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 + v_{6,1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tau^2 + v_{7,1} \end{pmatrix},$$

where the values for $v_{i,j}$ are given in Table 1, $v_{3,1,2} = 0.225$ as previously calculated, and τ^2 must be estimated using a generalized DerSimonian-Laird estimate or (restricted) maximum likelihood, as mentioned earlier.

In a network meta-analysis consisting of only 2-arm studies, equation (8) represents a weighted least squares problem since Σ is diagonal (but heteroskedastic). We address this weighted least squares problem in section 3.1. However, when multi-arm studies are present in the NMA, equation (8) becomes a generalized least squares problem (Aitken, 1936) due to the presence of non-zero correlations in Σ (such as in the example above). This more general problem is tackled separately in section 3.2.

3.1 Generalized Fused Lasso for NMA of 2-Arm Studies

Weighted least squares (WLS), or weighted linear regression, is a special case of generalized least squares. When observations are not equally reliable, they might be weighted, hence we should minimize the weighted sum of squares to get the best linear unbiased estimator $\hat{\mathbf{d}}$ by using formula:

$$\underset{\mathbf{d}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \|\mathbf{W}^{\frac{1}{2}}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\mathbf{d})\|_2^2, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = \Sigma^{-1}$ defines weights for each observation based on the standard error and heterogeneity in each contrast. In NMA of 2-arm studies, \mathbf{W} is a diagonal matrix and $\mathbf{W}^{1/2}$ can be calculated by taking the square root of each diagonal element in \mathbf{W} . By defining $\mathbf{y}^* = \mathbf{W}^{\frac{1}{2}}\mathbf{y}$, $\mathbf{X}^* = \mathbf{W}^{\frac{1}{2}}\mathbf{X}$, $\mathbf{E}^* = \mathbf{W}^{\frac{1}{2}}\epsilon^*$, and multiplying both sides of (8) by $\mathbf{W}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ from the left, the model becomes

$$\mathbf{y}^* = \mathbf{X}^*\mathbf{d} + \mathbf{E}^*, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{E}^* \sim MVN(\mathbf{0}, I), \quad (10)$$

and it will have the same least square estimates of \mathbf{d} as model (8) since $(\mathbf{X}^{*\prime}\mathbf{X}^*)^{-1}\mathbf{X}^{*\prime}\mathbf{y}^* = (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{y}$. Thus, this new formulation conforms to the requirements of the GFL methodology.

In order to penalize all $\binom{T}{2}$ pairwise comparisons similarly within the GFL framework, we re-express

problem (4) as

$$\underset{\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^{T-1}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y}^* - \mathbf{X}^* \mathbf{d}\|_2^2 + \lambda \sum_{i=2}^{T-1} |d_{1,i}| + \lambda \sum_{(i,j) \in E} |d_{1,i} - d_{1,j}|, \quad (11)$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ is the only tuning parameter. Since the $d_{1,i}$ are relative effects expressed relatively to a reference treatment 1, we define $G = (V, E)$ to be a complete graph (Bang-Jensen and Gutin, 2018) with $T - 1$ vertices, one per treatment excluding the reference treatment. In this complete graph, E is the set of all possible edges connecting the $T - 1$ vertices into pairs. In other words, E represents all the $\binom{T-1}{2}$ combinations of the $T - 1$ treatments. For instance, in our earlier example, the graph would have vertices $V = \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$ and edges $E = \{(2, 3), (2, 4), (2, 5), (3, 4), (3, 5), (4, 5)\}$.

Equivalently, we could formulate the problem in terms of the matrix D as in (2), which becomes

$$\underset{\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^{T-1}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y}^* - \mathbf{X}^* \mathbf{d}\|_2^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{D}^* \mathbf{d}\|_1, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{D}^* = (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{I}_{T-1})'$ with D the oriented incidence matrix of graph G . In other words, D is a matrix with a column for each vertex in E and a row for each edge in V . Each row is assigned a -1 and a 1 corresponding to the treatments in the edge (the orientation of the edge is arbitrary). All other elements are zero. For instance, for our earlier example, we would define

$$\mathbf{D}^* = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{D} \\ \mathbf{I}_{T-1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The solution $\hat{\mathbf{d}}(\lambda)$ to (11)-(12) can be obtained using the genlasso R package, with \mathbf{y}^* and \mathbf{X}^* as the response vector and design matrix, respectively, instead of the true \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{X} .

3.2 Generalized Fused Lasso for NMA with Multi-Arm Studies

When multi-arm studies are included in an NMA, there are non-zero values on the off-diagonal of the variance-covariance matrix Σ , thus $\mathbf{W} = \Sigma^{-1}$ is block-diagonal and a square root cannot be obtained as simply as in Section 3.1. To circumvent this issue, we decompose $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{U}'\mathbf{U}$, where \mathbf{U} is the upper triangular factor in a Cholesky decomposition (which can easily be calculated using the function *chol* in R). By defining $\mathbf{y}^\dagger = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{y}$, $\mathbf{X}^\dagger = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{X}$, $\mathbf{E}^\dagger = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{e}^*$ and multiplying both sides of (8) by \mathbf{U} , the model has the form (11) with $*$ replaced with \dagger and has the same least square estimates of \mathbf{d} as model (8) since $(\mathbf{X}^{\dagger'}\mathbf{X}^\dagger)^{-1}\mathbf{X}^{\dagger'}\mathbf{y}^\dagger = (\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{y}$. The GFL-NMA problem with multi-arm studies is equivalent to (11) where $*$ are replaced with \dagger . The solution to this problem, $\hat{\mathbf{d}}(\lambda)$, can be obtained using the genlasso R package using \mathbf{y}^\dagger and \mathbf{X}^\dagger as the response vector and design matrix, respectively, instead of the true \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{X} .

3.3 Selecting the Tuning Parameter

The GFL path algorithm solves the GFL equation for all values of $\lambda \geq 0$, but in practice, the value of λ must be tuned to balance fit and model complexity.

There are a variety of methods of selecting the parameters including Cross Validation (CV), Akaike

Information Criterion (AIC), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). Recommend by Chiquet et al. (2012), Jang et al. (2015) and Sennhenn-Reulen and Kneib (2016), AIC and BIC have the advantage of being easy to calculate based on the residual sum of squares (RSS). For the purpose of this paper, we prefer AIC as the criterion, because it is easy to calculate and by definition will select less complex models than BIC (Vrieze, 2012). Thus, it is less likely to select models with false pooling of treatments.

The AIC value of a statistical model is calculated by:

$$AIC(\lambda) = 2 \cdot \text{df}_\lambda + C \cdot \ln \left(\frac{RSS_\lambda}{C} \right),$$

where $C = \sum_{i=1}^M C_i$ is the sample size, df_λ are the degrees of freedom of the fitted model and $RSS_\lambda = \|\mathbf{y}^* - \mathbf{X}^* \hat{\mathbf{d}}(\lambda)\|_2^2$ (Section 3.1) or $\|\mathbf{y}^\dagger - \mathbf{X}^\dagger \hat{\mathbf{d}}(\lambda)\|_2^2$ (Section 3.2) is the residual sum of squares of the fitted model. The degrees of freedom in the GFL problem have a specific interpretation: they represent the expected number of non-zero fused groups (Tibshirani and Taylor, 2011). In practical terms, this means the number of treatment groupings (including singletons) which do not include the reference treatment, or the number of non-zero estimated parameters in $\hat{\mathbf{d}}(\lambda)$.

When the sample size is small, AIC is more likely to select models that have too many parameters, which may cause overfitting (Hurvich and Tsai, 1989). AICc is a variation on the AIC with a correction for small sample sizes. The formula for AICc is given by

$$AICc(\lambda) = AIC(\lambda) + \frac{2 \cdot \text{df}_\lambda (\text{df}_\lambda + 1)}{C - \text{df}_\lambda - 1}. \quad (13)$$

As $C \rightarrow \infty$, the correction term converges to 0, and thus AICc converges to AIC. In the rest of this paper, we will be using AICc as our model selection criteria. Smaller AICc values indicate better fitting models.

Define $\Delta AICc(\lambda) = AICc(\lambda) - AICc^{min}$ to denote the difference in AICc between the model at a specific λ value and the model with the smallest AICc among all $\lambda \geq 0$ values. As mentioned by Burnham and Anderson (2004), ΔAIC can be used to give both a quick strength-of-evidence comparison and ranking, and we use the same rule of thumb as this paper. The rule is given as: if $\Delta AIC \leq 2$, there is substantial support for the model, under λ , and the likelihood of the model compared to the best fitting model is at least 36%; if $4 < \Delta AIC \leq 7$ there is considerably less support for the model as the likelihood of the model compared to the best fitting model is between 3-14%; finally if $\Delta AIC > 10$, then there is essentially no support as the relative likelihood is less than 0.7%.

4 Simulation Study

In this section, we conduct a simulation study in order to investigate the performance and behaviour of the novel GFL-NMA approach under various scenarios. In each scenario, 1,000 \mathbf{y} values are randomly generated using model (8) with the network structure \mathbf{X} and $v_{i,j}$ values from Section 5.1's data application, which are provided in Table 1. Also, we set $\tau = 0$ similarly to Section 5.1. We consider four sets of values for \mathbf{d} , with various amounts of pooling, which will be presented in the next paragraph. For each of those values, we also consider three definitions of $v_{i,j}$. In one scenario, $v_{i,j}$ is set equal to the values in Table 1. Another scenario represents an extreme case of very little uncertainty in the data, where the $v_{i,j}$'s from Table 1 are multiplied by 0.1². Finally, the last scenario represents an extreme case where there is substantial uncertainty in the data, with the $v_{i,j}$'s from Table 1 multiplied by 10².

We define the vector of treatment effect $\mathbf{d} = (d_{12}, d_{13}, d_{14}, d_{15})'$, using treatment 1 as the reference

treatment. We first consider the case where all treatments have identical effects, i.e. $\mathbf{d} = (0,0,0,0)'$. For the second case, all treatment effects are different with $\mathbf{d} = (0.5,1,3,5)'$. For the third and fourth cases, some treatments have identical effects, with $\mathbf{d} = (1,1, - 2, - 2)'$ in the third case and $\mathbf{d} = (1,1,1, - 2)'$ in the fourth case. In other words, in the third case, treatments $\{2, 3\}$ and $\{4, 5\}$ have identical effects, while in the fourth case, treatments $\{2, 3, 4\}$ have identical effects, with other treatments having different effects.

Our simulation study answers the following questions of interest in each scenario. 1. What is the probability that accurate pooling occurs at least somewhere along the solution path? 2. If accurate pooling occurs somewhere along the solution path, how likely are we to give consideration to this model based on its $\Delta AICc$? 3. What is the probability that the lowest AICc model incorrectly pools at least one pair of treatments? 4. For each pairwise treatment comparison, what is the probability that the lowest AICc model pools these treatments? 5. For each pairwise treatment comparison, how does the mean square error of the estimate compare between the lowest AICc model and the full model?

In order to answer the questions above, we define, in each simulation, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ as the vector of critical λ values in the coordinate path, \mathbf{I} as the vector of variables indicating at each coordinate if treatment pooling was accurate (no false positive and no false negative) and \mathbf{FP} as the vector of variables indicating at each coordinate if any incorrect pooling occurred (false positives). Accordingly, define \mathbf{AICc} as the vector of AICc values at each coordinate. Let ι be the index of the smallest AICc model and $AICc^{\min} = \mathbf{AICc}_{\iota}$. In simulations with $\|\mathbf{I}\|_1 \geq 1$ (correct pooling occurs at least somewhere along the coordinate path), let λ^{opt} be the smallest λ value of models with a 1 in \mathbf{I} .

We answer questions 1 and 3 by estimating the joint probability function $p_{\iota} = P(\|\mathbf{I}\|_1 \geq 1, \mathbf{FP}_{\iota})$ as the proportion of simulations that fall in each of the four categories formed by crossing the two random variables indicating whether correct pooling occurs at least somewhere along the coordinate path and whether the lowest AICc model incorrectly pools at least one pair of treatments. We answer question 4 by calculating the proportion of simulations that pooled each pair of treatment in the lowest AICc model. Moreover, we answer question 2 from the empirical distribution of $\Delta AICc(\lambda^{\text{opt}})$ in simulations with $\|\mathbf{I}\|_1 \geq 1$ exclusively (since $\Delta AICc(\lambda^{\text{opt}})$ is undefined when $\|\mathbf{I}\|_1 = 0$). Finally, question 5 is answered by calculating the root mean square error (RMSE) of the lowest AICc model and the full model for each pairwise comparison.

Code for the simulation study is available as Supporting Information.

4.1 Results

The results for the simulation are summarized in Table 2 (addressing objectives 1, 3 and 4), Figure 1 (addressing objective 2), and Figure 2 (addressing objective 5).

\mathbf{d}'	Noise level	$\ \mathbf{I}\ _1 \geq 1$	$\mathbf{FP}_\ell = 1$	p_ℓ (%)	Pairwise probabilities of pooling for model ℓ (%)											
					1-2	1-3	1-4	1-5	2-3	2-4	2-5	3-4	3-5	4-5		
(0,0,0,0)	0.1	yes	yes no	100	80.5	83.9	82.7	84.4	75.8	81.4	81.1	83.8	83.0	86.6		
	1	yes	yes no	100	82.8	82.9	82.3	82.8	79.1	82.9	79.2	84.2	83.8	84.9		
	10	yes	yes no	100	82.4	81.9	81.8	84.3	78.4	82.2	79.6	83.5	83.5	84.0		
(0.5,1,3,5)	0.1	yes	yes no	100												
	1	yes	yes no	54.6 45.4	95.8	4.6	1.8					0.2				
	10	yes	yes no	99.1 ≤ 2	73.6	71.8	65.6	58.3	64.8	65.0	55.2	74.7	66.3	71.3		
(1,1,-2,-2)	0.1	yes	yes no	12.5					73.6						88.8	
		no	yes no	87.5					25.1						35.3	
	1	yes	yes no	≤ 2 10.1					81.1						91.1	
		no	yes no	39.8 48.1	36.7	92.5					29.1 34.9					30.4 36.0
	10	yes	yes no	≤ 2 ≤ 2					74.6	76.1	72.0	79.6	77.0	80.1		
		no	yes no	96.8 ≤ 2	79.4	80.1	74.3	75.3								
(1,1,1,-2)	0.1	yes	yes no	48.3					70.0	69.2			71.8			
		no	yes no	51.7					2.7	41.2			33.1			
	1	yes	yes no	≤ 2 44.7					67.3	74.3			76.5			
		no	yes no	7.8 46.3	34.6	84.6	51.3	5.1	19.2	43.6	5.1	50.0	5.1	5.1		
	10	yes	yes no	5.2 ≤ 2	92.3	92.3	92.3	73.1	100	100	69.2	100	69.2	69.2		
		no	yes no	92.6 ≤ 2	81.4	84.1	83.2	81.5	76.1	81.2	74.8	81.5	80.5	82.0		

Table 2: Probability estimates from each scenario of the simulation study. For ease of visualization, when $p \leq 2\%$, pairwise probabilities of pooling are not displayed. Other empty cells represent probabilities equal to zero. Grey shading is used to highlight, in each scenario, the treatments that are pooled in \mathbf{d} . Noise level represents the square root of the multiplier of $v_{i,j}$ which controls the uncertainty in different scenarios.

Figure 1: Under $\|\mathbf{I}\|_1 \geq 1$, the distribution of $|\Delta AICc(\lambda^{opt})|$ for different scenarios, labelled by \mathbf{d}' & noise level multiplier.

Figure 2: Root mean square error (RMSE) under the smallest AICc (best) model vs. full model in different scenarios and for all pairwise treatment comparisons. Black circles represent treatment comparisons that include the reference treatment while grey circles represent other treatment comparisons. The red line goes through the origin and has slope 1.

When the vector of treatment differences is set to $\mathbf{d} = (0,0,0,0)'$, Table 2 demonstrates that the coordinate path consistently includes the solution where all treatments are pooled. This is expected since increasing the regularization parameter λ ultimately leads to complete pooling of the treatments. In this case, incorrect pooling (false positives) also cannot occur. The results appear to be unaffected by the amount of variance in the data, as indicated by the noise level multiplier of $v_{i,j}$ in the simulations. Approximately 80% of the time, each pair of treatments is pooled together. In addition, Figure 1 illustrates that the model with the lowest AICc value tends to pool all treatments around 70% of the time. Otherwise, the model that pools all treatments is usually within a reasonable range of $\Delta AICc$ values to be given consideration. Finally, Figure 2 reveals that the RMSE of pairwise comparisons in the lowest AICc model is notably smaller than the full model. Overall, in this scenario, the Generalized Fused Lasso Network Meta-Analysis (GFL-NMA) approach outperforms the conventional NMA approach.

When the vector of treatment differences is set to $\mathbf{d} = (0.5,1,3,5)'$, Table 2 shows that the coordinate path consistently includes the solution where no treatments are pooled. This is expected since the case $\lambda = 0$ is always covered by the coordinate path. When the variability in the data is extremely small ($v_{i,j} \cdot 0.1^2$), false pooling never occurs and the lowest AICc always selects the full model, as desired (Figure 1). However, when the $v_{i,j}$'s are in a more typical range (with a noise level multiplier of 1), half of the simulations include at least one incorrect pooling, with a 95.8% probability that treatments 1 and 2 are incorrectly pooled, while other treatments are generally not pooled. This is not surprising since treatments 1 and 2 have the smallest pairwise difference (0.5) based on our definition of \mathbf{d} . Incorrectly pooling them improves model parsimony at a small cost in RMSE compared to the full model (Figure 2). Nonetheless, in approximately 80% of simulations, the full model should be given some consideration as $|\Delta AICc| \leq 7$ (Figure 1). Only in 0.3% of simulations, $|\Delta AICc| > 10$, indicating essentially no support for the full model. In scenarios with extremely large variability in the data (with noise level $v_{i,j} \cdot 10^2$), incorrect pooling is almost guaranteed (Table 2), and any pair of treatments is pooled with a probability between 55-75%. This is not surprising because as the variability in the data increases, treatment differences become overshadowed by the uncertainty in the estimated difference. Despite AICc clearly not favoring the full model (Figure 1), pooling of treatments is clearly beneficial in reducing the RMSE of treatment effect estimates (Figure 2). This finding suggests that incorrect pooling decisions may not necessarily be undesirable. When treatment differences are negligible compared to the uncertainty in the estimated difference, pooling treatments can both simplify the interpretation of the results and improve the accuracy of estimates.

When $\mathbf{d} = (1,1, -2, -2)'$, and the variability in the data is extremely small (with a noise level multiplier 0.1^2), Table 2 indicates that false pooling does not occur in the lowest AICc model. However, it often fails to pool treatments 2-3 and/or 4-5, with 87.5% of the simulations not containing the correct pooling configuration along the coordinate path. The RMSEs of the lowest AICc model are similar to the full model, indicating that the accuracy of the GFL-NMA approach is on par with the full model. When the $v_{i,j}$'s are in a more typical range (with noise level $v_{i,j}$), approximately 40% of the simulations include at least one incorrect pooling in the smallest AICc model, specifically either 1-2 or 1-3. This is not surprising since treatments 1-2 and 1-3 have the smallest non-zero pairwise difference based on our definition of \mathbf{d} . Incorrectly pooling them improves model parsimony at a small cost in RMSE, compared to the full model (Figure 2). In scenarios with extremely large variability in the data (with noise level $v_{i,j} \cdot 10^2$), incorrect pooling is almost guaranteed (Table 2), and any pair of treatments is pooled with a probability between 72-81%. This is not surprising because as variability in the data increases, treatment differences become drowned in the variability. Pooling of treatments is clearly beneficial in reducing the RMSE of treatment effect estimates (Figure 2). Again, this finding suggests that incorrect pooling decisions may be desirable in cases with high uncertainty, as they can simplify the model and improve the accuracy of estimates.

When $\mathbf{d} = (1,1,1, -2)'$, and the variability in the data is extremely small (noise level is $v_{i,j} \cdot 0.1^2$), Table 2 shows that false pooling never occurs in the lowest AICc model, however, it sometimes fails

to pool treatments 2, 3 and 4 correctly. Approximately half of the simulations included the correct pooling in the coordinate path and in over 80% of these simulations, the model with correct pooling should be given some consideration as $|\Delta AICc| \leq 7$ (Figure 1). The RMSEs of the lowest AICc model are similar to the full model indicating that accuracy of the GFL-NMA approach is on par with the full model. When the $v_{i,j}$'s are in a more usual range (multiplier of noise level equal 1), false pooling occurs in less than 10% of simulations and may involve any treatment but most likely 1-2, 1-3 or 1-4, which have the smallest treatment difference in **d**. Almost half of the simulations included the correct pooling in the coordinate path and in over 95% of these simulations, the model with correct pooling should be given some consideration as $|\Delta AICc| \leq 7$ (Figure 1). The RMSEs of the lowest AICc model are similar to the full model indicating that accuracy of the GFL-NMA approach is on par with the full model, while providing parsimony. When the variability in the data is extremely large (with noise level $v_{i,j} \cdot 10^2$) incorrect pooling is almost guaranteed (Table 2) and any pair of treatment is pooled with a probability above 70%. This is not surprising because as variability in the data increase, treatment differences would become drowned in the variability. This pooling of treatments is clearly beneficial in reducing the RMSE of treatment effect estimates (Figure 2). Again, this finding suggests that incorrect pooling decisions may be desirable in cases with high uncertainty.

5 Data Applications

In this section, we demonstrate the application of the method on two real-world datasets. The first dataset, analysed in section 5.1, was chosen to illustrate the method when the network of evidence is small (5 treatments, 7 studies). In contrast, the second dataset, analysed in section 5.2, was chosen to illustrate the method when the network of evidence is larger (10 treatments, 26 studies). Network plots of the datasets are presented in Figure 3. Code for both analyses is available as Supporting Information.

Figure 3: Network plots of the two datasets analysed. In each network, the thickness of edges is proportional to the number of studies implementing the comparison.

5.1 Parkinson's Dataset

The Parkinson's dataset (Dias et al., 2011) reports the mean off-time reduction in patients who received dopamine agonists as an adjunct therapy for Parkinson's disease. "Off" refers to periods when symptoms are not under control and smaller negative values of off-time reduction represent better outcomes (e.g. -2 is better than -1). The data, displayed in Table 1, includes differences in average off-time reduction and their corresponding standard errors between the intervention and control arms for each trial. The data may be obtained from the R package "netmeta". The network of evidence comprises seven studies involving five different drugs. One of the studies is a 3-arm study while all other studies have 2 arms. In this network, Placebo is represented by the label 1 as the reference

treatment, while the other drugs, namely Bromocriptine, Cabergoline, Pramipexole, and Ropinirole, are labelled as 2 to 5, respectively.

Plac (1)	0.48	0.48	0.76	1.72
0.48 [-0.48, 1.43]	Ropi (5)	0	0.28	1.24
0.52 [-0.41, 1.46]	0.05 [-0.59, 0.68]	Brom (2)	0.28	1.24
0.82 [-0.20, 1.85]	0.35 [-0.41, 1.10]	0.30 [-0.11, 0.71]	Cabe (3)	0.96
1.81 [1.16, 2.46]	1.33 [0.27, 2.40]	1.29 [0.26, 2.31]	0.99 [-0.11, 2.09]	Pram (4)

Table 3: League Table of pairwise comparisons for all treatments in the Parkinson’s dataset. The lower triangle presents estimates and 95% confidence intervals from fitting a standard (full model) NMA, while the upper triangle presents the GFL-NMA estimates of the lowest AICc model ($df = 3$, $\lambda = 0.193$). Differences are expressed as the treatment at the top/left compared to the treatment to the right/bottom. In the lower triangle, boldface is used to highlight statistically significant differences, and the boldface is reproduced symmetrically for ease of comparison between the methods.

Table 3 (lower triangle) and Figure 4 present the results of a conventional frequentist contrast-based NMA of these data. The analysis uses a fixed-effect model (as opposed to a random-effect model) since τ is essentially estimated as zero in these data (Franchini et al., 2012). Table 3 (lower triangle) displays a league table of all the pairwise treatment comparisons. Among these pairwise comparisons, three comparisons show statistical significance from zero: Pramipexole (the top-ranked treatment) compared to Placebo, Ropinirole, and Bromocriptine. Note that correction for multiple comparisons was not applied, as per usual in NMA. From Figure 4, it can be observed that Pramipexole has the highest probability of being ranked first, indicating the best treatment performance. On the other hand, Placebo has the poorest treatment performance, with a high likelihood of being ranked last. Cabergoline, Bromocriptine and Pramipexole are unlikely to be the best or worse treatments. Cabergoline has a high probability of being second best, while Bromocriptine and Ropinirole present similar ranking probabilities and are the most likely to be ranked third or fourth. Figure 4 also presents Surface Under the Cumulative RAnking curve (SUCRA) values, which are univariate summary measures of treatment rankings in a network meta-analysis. SUCRA values range from 0 to 1, where a higher value indicates better treatment performance (see e.g. Mbuagbaw et al. (2017)). Based on the SUCRA values, the rankings of the treatments from best to worst are as follows: Pramipexole, Cabergoline, Bromocriptine, Ropinirole, and Placebo. The difference in SUCRA between Bromocriptine and Ropinirole is minimal (0.06) while the differences in SUCRA values between the other treatments are more substantial, exceeding 0.21.

5.1.1 Generalized Fused Lasso Fixed-Effect Modelling with AICc selection

We implemented the GFL-NMA method proposed in Section 3 to the Parkinson’s dataset. Figure 5 shows the coordinate paths for the fitted generalized fused lasso model, and Table 4 provides AICc values at critical λ values. When $\lambda = 0$ (left of Figure 5), there is no lasso penalty and the estimates correspond to those of the full (standard) NMA model. As λ increases, paths merge gradually until all treatments are pooled with a common effect (Tibshirani and Taylor, 2011). To ensure the validity of our method, we conducted a sanity check by verifying that the least squares estimates obtained when $\lambda = 0$ (in our method) were equivalent to the estimates presented in the lower triangle of Table 3. These estimates also match the traditional least squares solution provided by Rucker and Schwarzer (2014), that is: $(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{y}$. The consistency of the estimates across all three methods provides reassurance about the correct implementation of our method.

In Table 4, although RSS for the full model ($df = 4$) is the smallest, the AICc value is significantly larger than the smallest AICc by 9.0. The trend in RSS is monotonically increasing, but AICc is the smallest when Bromocriptine and Ropinirole are pooled ($df = 3$, $\lambda = 0.193$), and then increases significantly when the next treatment is pooled to finally reduce to a value close to the full model’s

Figure 4: Probabilities of each treatment being at each possible rank (rank 1 being the best treatment). And the probabilities are calculated based on P-scores (Salanti et al., 2011).

AICc when all treatments are pooled. The upper triangle in Table 3 represents the estimated pairwise treatment effects under the lowest AICc model ($df = 3, \lambda = 0.193$). A single treatment difference is shrunk to 0, that is the comparison of Bromocriptine to Ropinirole. This outcome aligns with the observation that these two treatments displayed highly similar ranking patterns and had a minimal estimated difference of 0.05 in the full model analysis. Additionally, it is worth noting that none of the statistically significant effects from the previous full model analysis are pooled under the selected GFL-NMA model. This provides further confirmation that the GFL-NMA method produces results that align with expectations.

5.2 Diabetes Dataset

As a second case study, we consider a larger dataset, which compares the effects of several treatments on the HbA1c change from baseline in patients with type 2 diabetes (Senn et al., 2013). Elevated HbA1c values are indicative of diabetes. The data may be obtained from the R package “netmeta”. The dataset contains 25 two-arm studies and one three-arm study. There are 10 treatments in the network: Placebo (1), Acarbose (2), Benfluorex (3), Metformin (4), Miglitol (5), Pioglitazone (6), Rosiglitazone (7), Sitagliptin (8), Sulfonylurea (9), and Vildagliptin (10), and the network plot is shown as Figure 3b. We use Placebo as the reference treatment. The number beside the name or the first 4 letters in lowercase may be used to represent each treatment.

Figure 6 and Table 5 (lower triangle) present the results of a conventional frequentist contrast-based NMA of these data. The analysis uses a random-effect model with τ estimated as $\hat{\tau} = 0.3297$. Figure 6 indicates that Placebo is very likely to be the worst treatment and that Sulfonylurea is likely to rank second- or third-last. Sitagliptin, Vildagliptin, Benfluorex, Acarbose and Miglitol are unlikely to be ranked in the top 3 treatments, while Pioglitazone and Metformin are likely to rank in the top four, and Rosiglitazone in the top 3. Based on the SUCRA values, the rankings of the treatments from best to worst are as follows: Rosiglitazone, Metformin, Pioglitazone, Miglitol, Acarbose, Benfluorex, Vildagliptin, Sitagliptin, Sulfonylurea and Placebo. The difference in SUCRA between

Figure 5: Coordinate paths for the GFL-NMA model of the Parkinson's data. The solution $\hat{\mathbf{d}}(\lambda)$ is a continuous piece-wise linear function of λ . Treatments 1 to 5 are indicated on the right of the graph. The red dashed vertical line indicates a λ value where the model has the smallest AICc value.

df_λ	λ	RSS_λ	$AICc(\lambda)$	$\Delta AICc(\lambda)$
4	0.000	2.29	11.3	9.0
3	0.193	2.38	2.3	0.0
4	1.618	7.38	20.7	18.4
3	3.005	19.84	19.3	17.0
2	3.747	29.13	16.7	14.4
1	4.085	33.80	14.2	11.9
0	4.109	34.06	11.6	9.3

Table 4: Degrees of freedom, RSS and AICc values at λ values of merge points along the coordinate path. Note that $\lambda = 0$ corresponds to the full model. Values of λ larger than 4.109 are not displayed since all coordinate paths are fused past that point.

Vildagliptin-Benfluorex and between Pioglitazone-Metformin are minimal (≤ 0.03) while the differences in SUCRA values between the other treatments are more substantial, between 0.06 and 0.21.

Table 5 displays a league table of the results in its lower triangle, providing estimates and 95% confidence intervals for mean HbA1c change from baseline in all pairwise comparisons. Among these pairwise comparisons, Placebo is statistically different from all treatments except Sulfonylurea and Sitagliptin. In addition, Sulfonylurea is statistically different from Pioglitazone, Metformin and Rosiglitazone. No other comparison is statistically significant at the 5% significance level. Note that correction for multiple comparisons was not applied, as per usual in NMA.

Figure 6: Probabilities of each treatment being at each possible rank (rank 1 being the best treatment). And the probabilities are calculated based on P-scores (Salanti et al., 2011).

Figure 7: Coordinate paths for the GFL-NMA analysis of the diabetes data. The solution $\hat{\mathbf{d}}(\lambda)$ is a continuous piece-wise linear function of λ , however, the x -axis was transformed with a cubic root for ease of visualization. Treatments 1 to 10 are indicated on the right of the graph. The red dashed vertical line indicates a λ value where the model has the smallest AICc value.

5.2.1 Generalized Fused Lasso Random-Effect Modelling with AICc selection

We implemented the GFL-NMA method proposed in Section 3 to the diabetes dataset. Figure 7 shows the coordinate paths for the fitted generalized fused lasso model, and Table 6 provides AICc values at critical λ values. To ensure the validity of our method, we conducted the same sanity check as for the Parkinson's dataset: the least squares estimates obtained when $\lambda = 0$ were equivalent to the estimates presented in the lower triangle of Table 5 and matched the traditional least squares solution $(\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^{-1}\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{y}$.

df_λ	$\lambda^{\frac{1}{3}}$	RSS_λ	$AICc(\lambda)$	$\Delta AICc(\lambda)$
9	0.000	16.4	15.1	11.7
8	0.213	16.4	10.5	7.1
9	0.256	16.4	15.1	11.7
8	0.474	16.5	10.7	7.3
7	0.703	17.6	8.3	5.0
6	0.789	18.7	6.3	2.9
5	0.841	19.6	4.2	0.8
4	0.923	21.2	3.3	0.0
3	1.199	29.4	9.3	6.0
2	1.275	33.3	10.1	6.8
1	1.455	39.6	12.5	9.1
0	2.473	173.2	50.2	46.8

Table 6: Degrees of freedom, RSS and AICc values at λ values of merge points along the coordinate path. Note that $\lambda = 0$ corresponds to the full model. Values of $\lambda^{\frac{1}{3}}$ larger than 2.473 are not displayed since all coordinate paths are fused past that point.

In Table 6, although RSS for the full model ($df = 9, \lambda = 0$) is the smallest, the AICc value is significantly larger than the smallest AICc by 11.7. AICc is the smallest when Sitagliptin, Vildagliptin, Benfluorex, Acarbose, Miglitol and Pioglitazone are pooled together in a single group, while the

four other treatments are not pooled ($df = 3$, $\lambda^{\frac{1}{3}} = 0.193$). The models with $df = 5$ and $df = 6$ also deserve consideration based on their *AICc*. None of them pools Pioglitazone (6) and the latter also does not pool Miglitol (5).

The upper triangle in Table 5 represents the estimated pairwise treatment effects under the lowest *AICc* model, with $\lambda^{\frac{1}{3}} = 0.923$. The GFL model shrinks 15 out of 45 of the pairwise comparisons to 0. Notably, none of the significant effects from the previous full model analysis are pooled under the selected GFL-NMA model. From best to worse, treatments are ranked as Rosiglitazone, Metformin, “group of 6”, Sulfonylurea and Placebo with consecutive pairwise differences of 0.12, 0.11, 0.30 and 0.57. This ranking is coherent with SUCRA rankings from the full model analysis. It is interesting to note that Metformin and Pioglitazone are not pooled despite having an estimated treatment difference of 0.00 in the full model and SUCRA values within 0.01 of each other. As can be seen in Figure 7, their paths initially merged but quickly separated as λ increased. However, when inspecting Figure 6, their rank distributions clearly differ, with Pioglitazone having a monotonously decreasing distribution and Metformin’s distribution having a mode at ranks 2 and 3. This suggests that the pairwise difference estimate and SUCRA value alone may not fully capture all the information about treatment differences.

6 Discussion

In this paper, we introduced a novel approach for network meta-analysis that leverages the Generalized Fused Lasso to effectively shrink certain treatment differences to zero, thereby enhancing model parsimony. Our approach seamlessly integrates with the “genlasso” R package, delivering almost instantaneous results. Thus GFL-NMA emerges as an effective model selection strategy. As highlighted in Table 7, when dealing with networks containing a large number of treatments, the sheer volume of potential ways to pool these treatments can make fitting and evaluating all conceivable models computationally expensive or even infeasible. The computational efficiency of GFL-NMA and its freedom from prior assumptions regarding treatment similarities set it apart from existing Bayesian models discussed in Section 1. Our novel approach, like these models, holds the potential to address the ranking and multiple comparison issues within NMA, as previously mentioned in Section 1. For instance, treatments that are similar but are involved in relatively few trials might receive positively biased rankings, as noted by Kibret et al. (2014). However, our GFL-NMA approach can mitigate this bias by pooling these treatments, resulting in a larger number of trials within the pooled treatment group. Additionally, pooling treatments may substantially reduce the number of pairwise comparisons, thus assisting in addressing the multiple comparison issue. Further in-depth empirical investigations are warranted to thoroughly examine these properties.

T	Number of Pooling Variations	T	Number of Pooling Variations
1	1	11	678,570
2	2	12	4,213,597
3	5	13	27,644,437
4	15	14	190,899,322
5	52	15	1,382,958,545
6	203	16	10,480,142,147
7	877	17	82,864,869,804
8	4,140	18	682,076,806,159
9	21,147	19	5,832,742,205,057
10	115,975	20	51,724,158,235,372

Table 7: Number of ways to pool T treatments calculated by Stirling numbers of the second kind.

We gained valuable insights into the empirical performance of the GFL-NMA approach through a simulation study. In this study, we evaluated how well the novel approach performed under various

settings for the treatment effects. Drawing from arguments presented by Gelman and Tuerlinckx (2000) and Gelman et al. (2012), it is very unlikely for any treatment difference to be exactly zero in the real world. Thus, the second scenario, where treatment differences to the reference treatment were set to $\mathbf{d} = (0.5, 1, 3, 5)'$, is likely to be the most practically relevant to clinicians. Under this scenario with little uncertainty in the data, no pooling occurred in the lowest AICc model, as desired. When uncertainty in the data was moderate, the lowest AICc model often pooled the treatments with the smallest difference. This came with a small cost in mean square error in the pairwise comparisons. More investigation is required to understand how commonly this small cost occurs in other scenarios with moderate uncertainty. Considering the potential impact of incorrect pooling decisions, we recommend that practitioners approach pooling with caution and carefully assess all models within a reasonable range of $\Delta AICc$. Finally, the GFL-NMA approach showed advantages in scenarios with high uncertainty in the data by reducing mean square error through pooling treatments. This highlights the method's ability to simplify the model and improve accuracy under conditions when treatment differences are overshadowed by variability. Moreover, based on the findings in the literature, many experts, like Fu and Knight (2000), Greenshtein and Ritov (2004), Donoho (2006) and Bunea et al. (2007), have studied the ability of the lasso to recover the correct model as the amount of data and number of parameters increase. Specifically suggested by Donoho (2006), if the true model is sparse and we make certain assumptions on the model matrix \mathbf{X} , there should be a high probability that the solution will identify the correct predictors. Further work may be required to establish similar requirements for GFL-NMA.

In addition to the simulation study, we successfully applied the GFL-NMA approach to real-world datasets concerning Parkinson's and diabetes. The results obtained using the GFL-NMA approach were consistent with the conventional frequentist analyses, affirming the credibility of our proposed method. Moreover, the GFL-NMA method did not favor the full standard models since their AICcs were larger than models with the best pooling configurations by at least 9. These results suggest that analysis of real-world NMA datasets may benefit from pooling some treatments together to improve model parsimony.

The GFL-NMA approach comes with some limitations. One such limitation is that the least squares approach used in GFL does not assume normality of the response vector, which means it cannot provide traditional confidence intervals for the treatment effects. Nevertheless, at the model level, we can still quantify uncertainty using the ΔAIC measure, which provides a relative likelihood of different models (via $e^{-0.5\Delta AICc}$). To address the first limitation, a potential solution involves a two-step approach. In the first step, GFL-NMA is applied for model selection, and in the second step, a standard NMA model is fitted while assuming the treatment pooling configuration selected in the first step, as suggested in Hastie et al. (2017). An alternative one-step approach to overcome this limitation is the development of a Bayesian equivalent of GFL-NMA. In this Bayesian approach, shrinkage would be achieved through prior specifications, and credible intervals for treatment effects could be obtained directly. Another limitation of the current GFL-NMA approach is that it requires data to be expressed as contrasts, which may rely on approximations if the original data was extracted at the arm-level. Adapting GFL to handle these more complex data types directly may require further research and development.

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Supporting information

Code used to produce the simulation and data analysis results are openly available in a GitHub repository at https://github.com/Kxsssss/NMA_GFL.

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